

SELF-EFFICACY OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN RELATION TO THEIR GENDER AND CHANGE PRONENESS

Ranjana Kumari

Research Scholar, School of Education, Abhilashi University, Chailchowk, Mandi

Dr. Reena

Assistant Professor, School of Education, Abhilashi University, Chailchowk, Mandi

ABSTRACT

The present study was undertaken to investigate the self-efficacy of secondary school teachers in relation to their gender and change proneness. The study was conducted with the help of descriptive research method. A representative sample of 750 secondary school teachers was selected by employing incidental sampling technique. Teacher's Self-Efficacy Scale by Sood and Sen and Change Proneness Inventory by Dr. M. Mukhopadhyay were used to collect the necessary data. Descriptive statistics and Analysis of variance were used to analyze the data. The findings of the study indicated that male and female secondary school teachers possessed similar level of self-efficacy.

Secondary school teachers with different level of change proneness differed significantly from each other with regard to their self-efficacy. Gender and change proneness do not interact significantly with respect to self-efficacy of secondary school teachers.

KEYWORDS: Self-Efficacy, Gender, Change Proneness.

INTRODUCTION

Human beings are the unique creation of God, bestowed with many talents and skills, with their own temperament, potentiality and impairments. One cannot be compared with another. Regardless of how honest, straightforward, or practical someone may be, they will always have flaws, making them unique human beings. Every human being has a unique set of personal beliefs, points of view, tendencies, attitudes, and characteristics. Although each of them is distinct, the majority of them also have many characteristics, sentiments, and beliefs in common with other members of our society. Self-efficacy is one of the most significant behavioural factors that influences how people feel, think, and act. Self-efficacy relates to personal beliefs regarding competencies and abilities. Self-efficacy is a psychological concept that is described as a task-specific assessment of an individual's capacity to carry out a successful course of action, reflecting an individual difference variable. Bandura (1986) proposed that efficacy expectations may functionally predict whether or not one will undertake an action, the amount of effort put forth in pursuing that activity, and the degree of persistence in the face of challenges. Teachers' self-efficacy has gradually gained prominence in school psychology research due to its implications for teaching effectiveness, instructional practises, and students' academic achievement. Numerous studies have demonstrated that instructors who have high levels of self-efficacy report higher levels of job satisfaction, lower levels of stress at work, and fewer issues handling pupils' disruptive conduct. Therefore, striving to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of schools as well as the well-being of teachers may benefit greatly from understanding the key antecedents of self-efficacy. Change proneness is facilitated by radical change, innovativeness, a strong preference to inquire, shrewdness and proneness in thought, and exquisiteness. Innovativeness denotes not only the creation of new ideas, objects, or methods of doing something in a new and better way. It implies an open mind, a willingness to accept and adopt innovations when they are found useful and necessary for the advancement and development of oneself and one's organization. It is not change for the sake of change, but change to better achieve the objectives. Innovativeness is about more than just novelty. Therefore, the term "change proneness" can be used to describe the propensity

for changing one's behaviour, particularly in the professional realm and in relation to embracing innovation. This tendency can rely on the degree to which a person wants to change. As a result, it is critical to assess a person's attitude toward readiness for and susceptibility to change. **Raju (2013)** showed that significant differences were found between below 40 and above 40 years aged degree college lecturers, rural and urban teachers in their teacher motivation. It was also inferred from the study that change proneness and teacher motivation were significantly positively related. **Wyatt (2016)** highlighted the LTSE beliefs used in various fields, qualitative and mixed method design, highlighted the potential research directions for quantitative study. The results offered various suggestions that may be beneficial for teacher educator, researchers and implications for teacher education. **Sen and Sood (2016)** revealed that change proneness and self-efficacy are significantly and positively correlated. This means that the teachers with a tendency to accept new ideas, techniques in their teaching were more able to cope with their environment, realize their skills effectively and had a sense of higher self-efficacy. **Raju (2017)** concluded that change proneness differed significantly between male and female, B.Ed. assistant and secondary grades, below 35 years and above 35 years of age and below 15 years and above 15 years of experience. Further, it was also revealed that there were significant differences between B.Ed. assistant and secondary grades, rural and urban, below 35 years and above 35 years of age and below 15 years and above 15 years of experience teachers in their teachers efficacy. **Ashraf (2020)** concluded that self-esteem, self-efficacy and emotional intelligence had a significant and positive relationship with the organizational commitment of private secondary school teachers. Self-esteem, emotional intelligence and self-efficacy were found to be the significant predictors of organizational commitment. **Puju (2021)** concluded that 18.25% boys of senior secondary schools have high-level of self-efficacy, 65.00% boys of senior secondary schools had average level of self-efficacy whereas 16.75% boys of senior secondary schools had low level of self-efficacy. Whereas 18.00% girls of senior secondary schools have high-level of self-efficacy, 65.75% girls of senior secondary schools have average level of self-efficacy whereas 16.25% girls of senior secondary schools had low level of self-efficacy. **Somadi and Salendu (2022)** concluded that there was a positive and significant relationship between employee readiness to change, change leadership and effective commitment to change.

It has been observed on the basis of the thorough review of the literature that very few studies are on self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with respect to change proneness. Hence, it was decided to see the impact of gender and change proneness on self-efficacy of secondary school teachers.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with respect to their gender.
2. To study the difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with respect to their level of change proneness.
3. To study the interactional effect of gender and change proneness on self-efficacy of secondary school teachers.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. There exists no significant difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with respect to their gender.
2. There exists no significant difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with respect to their level of change proneness.
3. There exists no significant interactional effect of gender and change proneness on self-efficacy of secondary school teachers.

METHODOLOGY

Survey technique under descriptive research was used to achieve the objectives of the present study.

SAMPLING

In the present research, a representative sample of 750 secondary school teachers were selected from schools of Shimla, Solan and Sirmour districts of Himachal Pradesh by applying incidental sampling technique.

RESEARCH TOOLS USED

Teachers' Self-Efficacy Scale by Sood and Sen (2017) and Change Proneness Inventory by M. Mukhopadhyay (2012) were used for collection of data.

ANALYSIS OF DATA

Descriptive statistics and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to analyze the data. Detail of the analysis is given below:

In order to study the main and interactional effects of gender and level of change proneness on self-efficacy of secondary school teachers, Analysis of Variance (2x3 factor design) having two types of gender i.e. male and female and three levels of change proneness i.e. high, moderate and low, was applied on the mean scores of self-efficacy of secondary school teachers. The means and standard deviations of self-efficacy scores with respect to gender and level of change proneness are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1**MEANS AND STANDARD DEVIATIONS OF SELF-EFFICACY SCORES WITH REGARD TO GENDER AND CHANGE PRONESS**

Sr. No.	Level of Change Proneness (B) Gender (A)	Mean Self-Efficacy Scores				
		High Level	Moderate Level	Low Level	Total	
I	Male	Mean	231.92	229.39	223.04	228.76
		S.D.	42.598	33.465	29.283	34.649
		N	78	284	75	437
II	Female	Mean	239.07	236.40	222.67	234.80
		S.D.	32.396	28.159	23.275	28.521
		N	44	224	45	313
III	Total	Mean	234.50	232.48	222.90	231.28
		S.D.	39.238	31.401	27.084	32.352
		N	122	508	120	750

From the mean scores of self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with regard to gender and change proneness, 'F-Ratios' were calculated. The results are summarized in the Table 2 as follows:

TABLE 2**SUMMARY OF THE RESULTS OF ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE FOR SELF-EFFICACY OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER AND CHANGE PRONESS**

Sr. No.	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares (Variance)	F-Ratio
I	Gender (A)	2400.671	1	2400.671	2.332 ^{NS}
II	Change Proneness (B)	11143.359	2	5571.680	5.412*

III	Interaction (AxB)	1303.999	2	651.999	0.633 ^{NS}
IV	Error Variance	765906.884	744	1029.445	
V	Total	783924.759	749		

NS-Not-Significant

* Significant at 0.05 level of significance

(I) MAIN EFFECTS

(A) GENDER (A)

From the above Table 2, it is evident that the calculated value of ‘F-Ratio’ for the main effect of gender on the self-efficacy of secondary school teachers, for a degree of freedom 1 and 744, was found to be 2.332 which is below the F-table value 3.85 even at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the Hypothesis no.1 that, “There exists no significant difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with respect to their gender” was retained. Thus, it is interpreted that male and female secondary school teachers possessed similar level of self-efficacy. Although, female secondary school teachers possessed high level of self-efficacy (Mean-234.80) as compared to male secondary school teachers (Mean-228.76). The mean self-efficacy scores of male and female secondary school teachers were shown in Figure 1 as follows:

**FIGURE 1
MEAN SELF-EFFICACY SCORES OF MALE AND FEMALE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS**

(B) CHANGE PRONENESS (B)

The calculated value of 'F' for finding the main effect of change proneness on self-efficacy of secondary school teachers, for degrees of freedom 2 and 744, came out to be 5.412, which is greater than the F-table value 4.63 at 0.01 level of significance. Hence, the Hypothesis no. 2 that, “There exists no significant difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with respect to their level of change proneness” was not accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that secondary school teachers with different level of change proneness differed significantly from each other with regard to their self-efficacy.

The Figure 2 shows the mean self-efficacy scores of secondary school teachers with respect to level of change proneness.

FIGURE 2
MEAN SELF-EFFICACY SCORES OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS WITH DIFFERENT LEVEL OF CHANGE PRONENESS

In order to study the significant difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with regard to different level of change proneness, statistical technique of ‘t’ test was applied, details of which are given below:

(i) SELF-EFFICACY OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS WITH RESPECT TO HIGH CHANGE PRONENESS AND MODERATE CHANGE PRONENESS

Table 3 shows the value of means, standard deviations, standard error of difference between means and t- value.

TABLE 3
‘T’ VALUE SHOWING THE SIGNIFICANCE OF DIFFERENCE IN MEAN SELF-EFFICACY SCORES OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN RELATION TO HIGH AND MODERATE LEVEL OF CHANGE PRONENESS

Sr.No.	Comparison Groups	N	Mean	SD	df	SED	t-Value
1	High Change Proneness	122	234.50	39.238	628	3.33	0.605 ^{NS}
2	Moderate Change Proneness	508	232.48	31.401			

NS-Non Significant

The calculated value of ‘t’ for finding out the significance of mean difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with high and moderate level of change proneness came out to be 0.605 which is not significant even at 0,05 level of significance, for df 628 . Hence, it may be said that there is no significant difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with high and moderate level of change proneness.

(ii) SELF-EFFICACY OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS WITH RESPECT TO HIGH CHANGE PRONENESS AND LOW CHANGE PRONENESS

The means, standard deviations, standard error of difference between means and t- value were given in Table 4 as follows:

TABLE 4

‘T’ VALUE SHOWING THE SIGNIFICANCE OF DIFFERENCE IN MEAN SELF-EFFICACY SCORES OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN RELATION TO HIGH AND LOW LEVEL ,OF CHANGE PRONENESS

Sr.No.	Comparison Groups	N	Mean	SD	df	SEd	t-Value
1	High Change Proneness	122	234.50	39.238	240	4.34	2.672**
2	Low Change Proneness	120	222.90	27.084			

****Significant at 0.01 Level of Significance**

It was observed from the Table that the obtained value of ‘t’ for testing the significance of difference, came out to be 2.672 which is greater than the table value 2.59 at 0.01 level of significance, for df 240. Therefore, it may said that there exists significant difference in the self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with respect to high and low level of change proneness. Further, mean scores of secondary school teachers with high level of change proneness is 234.50, which is higher than the mean score of secondary school teachers with low level of change proneness i.e. 222.90. Hence, secondary school teachers having high level of change proneness possessed high self-efficacy as compared to secondary school teachers having low level of change proneness.

(iii)SELF-EFFICACY OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS WITH RESPECT TO MODERATE CHANGE PRONENESS AND LOW CHANGE PRONENESS

The means, standard deviations, standard error of difference between means and t- value were given in Table 5.

TABLE 5

‘T’ VALUE SHOWING THE SIGNIFICANCE OF DIFFERENCE IN MEAN SELF-EFFICACY SCORES OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN RELATION TO MODERATE AND LOW LEVEL OF CHANGE PRONENESS

Sr.No.	Comparison Groups	N	Mean	SD	df	SED	t-Value
1	Moderate Change Proneness	508	232.48	31.401	626	3.10	3.083**
2	Low Change Proneness	120	222.90	27.084			

****Significant at 0.01 Level of Significance**

The calculated value of ‘t’ for finding the significance of mean difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers having moderate and low level of change proneness, came out to be 3.083 which is significant at .001 level of significance for df 626. It means that secondary school teachers having moderate level of change proneness differed significantly from secondary school teachers having low level of change proneness with respect to their self-efficacy. Further, from mean scores, it may be inferred that secondary school teachers possessing moderate level of change proneness (232.48) have better self-efficacy as compared to secondary school teachers possessing low level of change proneness (222.90).

(II) INTERACTIONAL EFFECT (AXB)

The calculated value of ‘F-Ratio’ for the interactional effect of gender and change proneness on self-efficacy of secondary school teachers, for a degree of freedom 2 and 744, came out 0.633. This value is below the F-table value 3.00 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the Hypothesis no. 3 that, “There exists no significant interactional effect of gender and change proneness on self-efficacy of secondary school teachers” was retained. It means that gender and change proneness do not interact significantly with respect to self-efficacy of secondary school teachers. Therefore, it may be interpreted that the

gender and change proneness taken together did not affected self-efficacy of secondary school teachers significantly.

CONCLUSION

1. Male and female secondary school teachers possessed similar level of self-efficacy. Although, female secondary school teachers possessed high level of self-efficacy (Mean-234.80) as compared to male secondary school teachers (Mean-228.76).
2. Secondary school teachers with different level of change proneness differed significantly from each other with regard to their self-efficacy. There was no significant difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with high and moderate level of change proneness. Secondary school teachers having high level of change proneness possessed high self-efficacy as compared to secondary school teachers having low level of change proneness. Secondary school teachers possessing moderate level of change proneness (232.48) have better self-efficacy as compared to secondary school teachers possessing low level of change proneness (222.90).
3. Gender and change proneness do not interact significantly with respect to self-efficacy of secondary school teachers. Therefore, it may be interpreted that the gender and change proneness taken together did not affected self-efficacy of secondary school teachers significantly.

IMPLICATIONS

The present study was undertaken to study the self-efficacy of secondary school teachers in relation to their gender and change proneness. After drawing out the results from the study, it was revealed that that there was no significant difference in self-efficacy of male and female secondary school teachers. Although female secondary school teachers possessed high level of self-efficacy (Mean-234.80) as compared to male secondary school teachers (Mean-228.76). Hence, there is a great need of increasing self-efficacy of male secondary school teachers. It was further revealed that secondary school teachers with different level of change proneness differed significantly from each other with regard to their self-efficacy. Secondary school teachers having high level of change proneness possessed high self-efficacy as compared to secondary school teachers having low level of change proneness. Secondary school teachers possessing moderate level of change proneness have better self-efficacy as compared to secondary school teachers possessing low level of change proneness. This means that teachers' tendency to accept new ideas, to cope with new teaching techniques are more able to cope with their environment. This will lead to high self-efficacy among teachers. High self-efficacy among teachers will lead towards effective teaching and good students' performance. Hence, efforts should be made to increase change proneness ability and self-efficacy of teachers. This will not only lead to the improvement in satisfaction level of teachers but also improve the commitment towards their profession.

REFERENCES

1. Ashraf, N. (2020). *Study of organizational commitment among secondary School Teachers in relation to emotional intelligence self esteem and self efficacy* (Doctoral dissertation, Aligarh Muslim University, Uttar Pradesh, India). Retrieved from <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/handle/10603/354030> on dated 12-12-2023.
2. Pujju, B. A. (2021). *Role of social support and self efficacy on student engagement among senior secondary school students*. (Ph.D. thesis, Lovely Professional University, Jalandhar, India). Retrieved from <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/handle/10603/329161> on dated 11-12-2023.

3. Raju, T.J.M.S. (2013). Relationship between change proneness and teacher motivation among degree college teachers. *International Educational E-Journal*, 02(02), 20-25.
4. Raju, T.J.M.S. (2017).). Change proneness in relation to teacher efficacy among secondary School Teachers. *Conflux Journal of Education*, 5(3), 13-20.
5. Sood, V. & Sen, S. (2016). Self-efficacy as related to gender, teaching experience and change proneness among secondary school teachers. *Scholarly Research Journal for Humanity Science and English Language*, 3(18), 4068-4078.
6. Somadi, N. & Salendu, A. (2022). Mediating role of employee readiness to change in the relationship of change leadership with employees' affective commitment to change. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute (BIRCI-Journal): Humanities and Social Sciences*, 5(1), 30-38.
7. Wyatt, M. (2018). Language Teachers' Self-efficacy Beliefs: A Review of the Literature (2005-2016). *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(4). Retrieved from <http://ro.ecu.edu.au/ajte/vol43/iss4/6>. on dated 11-11-2023.